

Signs and symptoms of diabetes

There are some problems that can be caused by diabetes.

- Always feeling tired
- Not seeing well
- Losing weight even though you eat well
- Going to the toilet often
- Feeling very, very thirsty
- Itchiness of private parts
- Sexual dysfunction
- Sores and wounds that do not heal

These are also signs of diabetes. If a person may experience any of these symptoms, one should get tested for diabetes.

Always feeling tired

Storyboard while *always feeling tired* is presented

Illustration of not seeing well

Illustration of losing weight even though you eat well

Illustration of going to the toilet often

Illustration of feeling very, very thirsty

Illustration of Itchiness of private parts

Illustration of Sexual dysfunction

Illustration of sores and wounds that do not heal